

2024 NASA Software Workshop Agenda

Website: <https://science.data.nasa.gov/news/software-workshop-2024/>

[Overall Google Folder](#)
[Discussion Topic Padlet](#)
[Q&A Tool](#)

Please see your email for the WebEx link and passcode.

Tuesday, May 7, 2024

Time (ET)	Agenda Item	Presenter/Notes/Links
Day 1, Session 1: Software at NASA - Opportunities and Challenges		Day 1 Google Folder Moderator: Mark Parsons
8:30am	Check in and registration	
9:30 am - 9:50 am	Welcome and Purpose	Kevin Murphy and Steve Crawford
9:50 am - 10:05 am	Organization, Logistics, and Questions Submissions	Rebecca Ringuette
10:05 am - 10:25 am	Invited Talk 1	Tasha Snow
10:25 am - 10:45 am	Invited Talk 2	Bill Wohler
10:45 am - 11:05 am	Invited Talk 3	Dan Crichton
11:05 am - 11:10 am	Discussion Topics Submissions	Rebecca Ringuette
11:10 am	<i>Break (15 minutes)</i>	
11:25 am - 12:10 pm	Questions and Structured Discussion	Tasha Snow, Bill Wohler, and Dan Crichton
12:10 pm - 1:40 pm	<i>Lunch (1 hour 30 min)</i>	

Day 1 Session 2: Software and Policy		Day 1 Google Folder Moderator: Steven Crawford
1:40 pm - 2:00 pm	Invited Talk on Policy and Processes	Matt Palmer
2:00 pm - 2:55 pm	Software, Policy and Processes at NASA <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Introduction (4 min) ● STRIVES (5 min) ● NPR 7150 (20 min) ● Software Release Process (20 min) ● Lightning Talks (6 min) 	Steve Crawford, JoAnne Calhoun, Scott Tashakkor, Chris Copelan and Kimberly Minafra, Miguel Martinho, Lauren Sanders
2:55 pm - 3:15 pm	Open Discussion	N/A
3:15 pm - 3:30 pm	<i>Break (15 minutes)</i>	
3:30 pm - 3:40 pm	Logistics of Breakouts	Steve Crawford
3:40 pm - 4:10 pm	Software Policy and Processes at NASA Retrospective	(See Breakout Folder)
4:30 pm - 5:00 pm	Report Back, Q+A, and Wrap Up	Steven Crawford

Wednesday, May 8, 2024

<i>Time (ET)</i>	<i>Agenda Item</i>	<i>Presenter/Notes</i>
Day 2: Community Software Efforts at NASA - Opportunities and Challenges		Day 2 Google Folder Morning Moderator: Demitri Muna Afternoon Moderator: Brian Thomas
9:30 am - 9:50 am	Invited Talk on Community Software Efforts at NASA	Julie Barnum
9:50 am - 10:30 am	Software at NASA: Highlighted Talks with Q&A	Ross Beyer Luis Lopez David Aronchick Ziheng Sun

10:30 am - 10:55 am	Logistics of Breakouts	Rebecca Ringuette
10:55 am - 11:40 am	Software at NASA: Lightning Breakout 1	(See Lightning Folder)
11:40 am - 11:55 am	<i>Break (15 minutes)</i>	
11:55 am - 12:30 pm	Software at NASA: Lightning Breakout 2	(See Lightning Folder)
12:30 pm - 2:00 pm	<i>Lunch (1.5 hours)</i> (Voting open over lunch)	
2:00 pm - 2:15 pm	Breakout logistics and voting (Plenary)	Rebecca Ringuette
2:15 pm - 3:00 pm	Software at NASA: Discussion Breakout 1 Lightning sessions 1B and 1E	(See Discussion Folder)
3:00 pm - 3:15 pm	<i>Break (15 minutes)</i>	
3:15 pm - 3:30 pm	Breakout logistics	Rebecca Ringuette and Holly Norton
3:30 pm - 4:15 pm	Software at NASA: Discussion Breakout 2	(See Discussion Folder)
4:15 pm - 5:00 pm	Report Back and Paths Forward	Brian Thomas

Thursday, May 9, 2024

Time (ET)	Agenda Item	Presenter/Notes
	Day 3: Priorities of Topics Of Interest, Deeper Diver on Exploring the Highest Community Priorities, and Summary	Day 3 Google Folder Moderator: Mark Parsons
9:30 am - 9:40 am	Funding for Software at NASA	Demitri Muna Eric Ting

9:40 am - 10:00 am	Discussion Prioritization and Breakout Logistics	Steve Crawford
10:00 am - 10:45 am	Paths Forward: Breakout Session 1	(See Discussion Folder)
10:45 am - 11:00 am	<i>Break (15 minutes)</i>	
11:00 am - 11:45 am	Paths Forward: Breakout Session 2	(See Discussion Folder)
11:45 am - 12:30 pm	Report Back and Wrap Up	Steve Crawford
12:30 pm - 2:00 pm	<i>Lunch (1 hour and 30 minutes)</i>	
2:00 pm - 3:45 pm	Next Steps and Report Outline	Mark Parsons
